

Special Care Dentistry for Developmentally Disabled Child

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Abstract

Special Care Dentistry (SCD) focuses on enhancing oral health for individuals with diverse impairments, including physical, sensory, intellectual, and medical conditions. It highlights the significant prevalence of disabilities in India and globally, as well as the complex nature of disability according to the WHO International Classification of Functioning. It discusses the extended lifespan of children with special healthcare needs (CSHCN) due to medical advancements, necessitating tailored dental care to manage associated oral health challenges. Despite global efforts to improve oral health, disadvantaged and disabled populations continue to face disparities. It concludes by outlining the scope of a forthcoming library dissertation, which aims to review prevalent oral conditions among individuals with special needs and propose general care recommendations to address their unique challenges in accessing dental treatment.

Keywords : Special Care Dentistry (SCD), Children with Special Healthcare Needs (CSHCN), impairment or disability, oral health challenges.

Introduction

Special Care Dentistry is concerned with providing and enabling the delivery of oral care to people with impairment or disability.

“Disabled” does not mean worthless... it’s never about productivity; it’s about humanity - Crane (998)¹.

“The maintenance of general and oral health in these children poses significant challenges, and their teeth are frequently compromised by extensive caries and periodontal conditions.” Hence, the management of these “God’s forgotten children” is a task that needs special effort on the part of the dental surgeon and pediatric dentist¹. The number of children with disabilities is increasing, largely due to advancements in medical technology and treatment. These medical breakthroughs have enabled the survival of children who, in the past, might not have lived, often resulting in long-term disabilities. Furthermore, modern medicine has significantly extended the life expectancy of children with complex conditions. As with all paediatric patients, delivering effective dental care to this group requires a holistic approach one

that considers the overall well-being of the child and family, not just their oral health. Like all children, those with special needs are individuals with distinct personalities, interests, family dynamics, strengths, and challenges. While a diagnosis can offer valuable insight into a child’s medical, dental, and behavioural considerations, it does not define the child entirely. Two children with the same condition - such as autism or cerebral palsy - may have vastly different needs. Providing dental care to these children is not only a challenge but also a privilege and a source of joy, as it involves understanding each child uniquely and tailoring an approach that supports lifelong oral health². Thus, this library dissertation aims to discuss the factors and the techniques for managing special children in dental operatories.

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Definitions And Terminologies

The handicapped one umbrella term which has been given by the WHO in 1963 and different terminologies from then have been evaluated for special childlike impairment Handicap, Disable, Children with special health care needs, Gods Forgotten Child etc.

1. Special Care Dentistry

The improvement of oral health of individuals and groups in society who have a physical, sensory, intellectual, mental, medical, emotional or social impairment or disability or, more often, a combination of a number of these factors.³

According to the American Association of Paediatric Dentistry (2013)⁴ defines special health care needs as “any physical, developmental, mental, sensory behavioural, cognitive or emotional impairment or limiting condition that requires medical management, health care intervention and/or use of specialized services or programs.”

2. Impairment

Impairment is defined as any loss or abnormality in psychological, physiological, or anatomical structure or function—such as loss of vision or hearing. A primary impairment can give rise to secondary issues; for example, hearing loss may contribute to learning difficulties and reduced academic performance. Impairment often progresses to disability.

3. Disability

According to Centres for Disease Control and Prevention (2018)⁵ Developmental disabilities refer to a group of conditions resulting from impairments in physical, cognitive, language, or behavioral functions. These conditions typically emerge during the developmental period, affect daily functioning, and are often lifelong.

4. Handicapped Or Challenged

According to World Health Organization (1980)⁴ defines a handicapped individual as “one who, over an appreciable time, is prevented by a physical or mental condition from full participation in the normal activities of his age group, including those of a social, recreational education and vocational nature.”

5. Children With Special Healthcare Needs (CSHCN)⁶

According to the American Academy of Paediatric Dentistry is an age-defined specialty that provides both primary and comprehensive preventive and therapeutic oral health care for infants and children through adolescence, including those with special health care needs.

Classification

The special child has been classified into various categories according to different authors which has listed below:

1. Frank and Winter (1974)⁴
 - a) Blind or partially blind
 - b) Deaf or partially deaf
 - c) Educationally subnormal
 - d) Epileptic
 - e) Maladjusted
 - f) Defective in speech
 - g) Senile

2. Agerholm (1975)⁷
 - a) Intrinsic
 - b) Extrinsic
3. Convenience of Management (1975)⁴
 - a) Developmentally disabled child
 - b) Medically compromised child

Flowchart : Classification of Special Child

4. According to Nowak(1976)⁴
 - a) Physically handicapped
 - b) Mentally handicapped
 - c) Congenital defects
 - d) Convulsive disorders
 - e) Communication disorders
 - f) Systemic disorders
 - g) Metabolic disorder

5. According to Damle(2000)¹
 - a) Physical handicap e.g. monoplegia, paraplegia
 - b) Mental handicap e.g. Down syndrome
 - c) Sensory handicap e.g. Deafness, Blindness
 - d) Medically compromised e.g. Hemophilia, Leukemia
 - e) Multi-handicap Multiple handicapping conditions
 - f) Dentally handicapped with oral abnormality.

The Ethos of Special Care Dentistry³

The foundation of Special Care Dentistry lies in its comprehensive, patient-centered philosophy of care. It prioritizes a holistic approach to oral health by collaborating with all members of an individual’s care team - whether dental, medical, or social - to develop the most suitable care plan through an integrated pathway. Special Care Dentistry is proactive in addressing the needs of individuals with disabilities, rather than responding only when issues arise. It acknowledges that certain individuals may face barriers to accessing oral healthcare independently or expressing their needs. Therefore, it emphasizes tailored screening, prevention, and treatment programs designed to meet the unique requirements of specific groups or individuals.

Common Oral Health Problems And Management In Special Needs Care Children

Trauma	Tooth wear	Bruxism ⁸	Caries
Erosion	Periodontal disease	Drooling	Dry mouth
Mucosal disease	Biting	Oral Candidiasis	Halitosis

Oral Health Care For Special Child⁸

In addition to providing safe and adequate dental care, oral health care for people with special needs emphasizes the importance of enhancing these populations' oral health status through the implementation of efficient preventative measures. The creation of clinical guidelines and integrated care pathways to help remove obstacles to oral health treatment can help achieve these goals.

- A) Barriers To Oral Health Care
- Barriers concerning the individual
 - Barriers concerning the dental profession
 - Barriers concerning government

- B) General Consideration for the Treatment of Special Child in Dental Office
- Dental Office Access
 - Behavior Management
 - Dental Radiograph
 - Special Modification for Invasive Dental Procedures
 - Consideration For Sedation

Developmental Disability⁹

It is a severe, chronic disability that may impact physical functioning, cognitive abilities, or both. These disabilities are likely to last a lifetime and manifest before the age of 22. In addition to intellectual disabilities, physical disabilities are often included in the phrase “developmental disability.”

Most common developmental disabilities which are encountered in paediatric dental clinics are:

1. Mental Retardation	2. Down Syndrome	3. Epilepsy
4. Cerebral Palsy	5. Autism	

Mental Retardation

Mental retardation (MR) is one of the most common developmental disabilities. It is a source of pain and bewilderment to many families. Sheerenberger (1983) classifies that disability of the brain and mind occurs due to brain damage. One of the major differences is that they are slow learners, thus these kids do not grow at an average rate and exhibit great difficulty in learning and productivity¹⁰.

Classifications¹

According to Degree <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Mild Moderate Severe Profound 	According to Origin <table style="width: 100%; border: none;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%; border: none;"> *Syndromic Mental retardation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Down syndrome Prader-Willi syndrome Cri du chat syndrome Rett syndrome </td> <td style="width: 50%; border: none;"> *Non-syndromic Mental retardation </td> </tr> </table>	*Syndromic Mental retardation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Down syndrome Prader-Willi syndrome Cri du chat syndrome Rett syndrome 	*Non-syndromic Mental retardation
*Syndromic Mental retardation <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Down syndrome Prader-Willi syndrome Cri du chat syndrome Rett syndrome 	*Non-syndromic Mental retardation		

Classification	According to IQ score
Mild MR	55-70
Moderate MR	40-54
Severe MR	25-39
Profound MR	Below 25

AETIOLOGY		
Prenatal	Natal	Postnatal
Genetic disorders	Birth injuries	Cerebral infections
Maternal and fetal infections	Infection	Cerebral trauma
Kernicterus	Cerebral	Poisoning
Cretinism	Haemorrhage	Cerebrovascular
Prenatal unknown	Hypoxia	
Fetal alcohol	Anoxia	
	Hypoglycaem	

Oral Manifestations ⁴	
Baby-bottle tooth decay/early childhood caries, malocclusions	
Poor dental hygiene, dental plaque, and gingivitis, bruxism.	
Injurious behavior can arise in people with severe and profound Mental retardation. For example, lip biting or additionally biting the buccal mucosa. Lesch - Nyhan syndrome has the same features and includes biting the digits of the hand.	

Treatment consideration for mental retardation			
Dental management	Behavioral Strategies	Management Aids	Radiographic Examination
*Proper Medical History *Dental History *Behavioral History	*Avoiding/minimizing painful/fear-evoking stimuli *Reinforcement of appropriate response *Promoting relaxation using pre-medication. *Brief and early morning appointments are suitable *Get the patient familiar with the dentist, dental staff, and dental office before the treatment begins	*Papoose board for complete patient restraint *Tie-type arm and leg restraints *Seat belt-type straps *Extra personnel. *Intra-oral management aids such as Molt's mouth prop.	*Should be done on the second visit *Intra-oral films with bite tags *Films should be supported with dental floss *Proper radiation hazard protection
Follow-up Care	Individuals should be evaluated at least annually by a neurologist or a pediatrician for management		

Down's Syndrome

Down syndrome is a chromosome disorder associated with an extra chromosome (Trisomy 21) resulting in intellectual disability and specific physical features¹¹.

John Langdon Down (1862)¹² first characterized Down Syndrome as a distinct form of mental disability.

In 1959, the French physician Jerome Lejeune identified Down Syndrome as a syndrome as a chromosomal condition.

Incidence/Prevalence: It is found to occur 1 in every 700 live births (<1%).

Types

Three types of chromosomal abnormalities can lead to Down syndrome which is summarised in the below table.

- Medical complications seem to be similar in all three groups⁹.

Types	
Down's syndrome	Nondisjunction-95% (Males 59%, females 41%)
	Translocation-4% (Females 74%, males 26%)
	Mosaicism-1% (may have more subtle feature)

Predisposing Factors and Causes

1. Advanced maternal age
2. Uterine and placental abnormalities
3. Chromosomal aberrations

Oral Manifestations		
<p><u>Mouth</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Small drooping mouth *Open mouth posture Tongue *Protrusive, fissured (scrotal) tongue. 	<p><u>Lips</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Thick, dry, fissured <p><u>Occlusion</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Anterior open bite and crossbite, class III tendency, small maxilla <p><u>Occlusion</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Anterior open bite and crossbite, class III tendency, small maxilla 	<p><u>Palate</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *omega palate *Bifid uvula, cleft lip and palate <p><u>Teeth</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *Hypodontia, Microdontia. *Hypocalcification and hypoplastic defects. <p><u>Periodontium</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> *poor oral hygiene, malocclusions and systemic factors such as decreased humoral response.
*Macroglossia	*Anterior open bite and crossbite, class III tendency, small maxilla	defects. <u>Periodontium</u> *poor oral hygiene, malocclusions and systemic factors such as decreased humoral response.

Management of Down Syndrome in Dental Office

<p><u>Behavioral Management Considerations</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Early morning appointments Talk with the parent or caregiver- explain each procedure short and clear instructions. Avoid abrupt distractions, such as sights and sounds. Always use the tell-show-do approach 	<p><u>Treatment Consideration</u></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pleasant, cheerful, affectionate and cooperative, and dental procedures can be provided without compromise. Work at a slower pace. Follow up visit to monitor oral hygiene like fluoride application, pit and fissure sealants, silver diamine fluoride, etc. Light sedation or severely resistant patients may require general anaesthesia.
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Epilepsy

The word "epilepsy" is derived from the Greek word "epilambanein" meaning to take or to seize.

Hippocrates recognized that seizure-res originated in the brain.⁸

Epilepsies are a group of disorders characterized by chronic, recurrent, and paroxysmal changes in neurological function caused by abnormalities in the electrical activity of the brain.

The incidence of epilepsy is approximately 1%.

Fig: Sign And Symptoms of Epilepsy

Classification of Epilepsy¹³

<p>Partial Only part of the cortex is disrupted</p> <p>Simple Complex</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Motor • sensory • Autonomic • Psychic 	<p>Generalized All of the cortex is disrupted</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tonic-clonic • Absence: - Typical & Atypical • Myoclonic • Atonic • Clonic • Tonic
<p>Injuries Caused by the Fit</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soft tissue lacerations of tongue or buccal mucosa • Facial fractures • Trauma to teeth - avulsion, luxation, fractures • Subluxation of the Temporo-Mandibular Joint 	

Oral Manifestations of Epilepsy⁹

Dental Management of the Epileptic patient¹³

- Take a complete health history
- List medications the patient is taking* (any specific oral effects)
- Schedule proper frequency of oral hygiene
- Ensure proper dental lighting (no light directly in the eyes).
- Ensure medications have been taken properly – to minimize the risk of seizure.
- Perform proper periodontal and surgical treatment of gingival hyperplasia to minimize damage to teeth and supporting structures and to maintain proper aesthetics.
- If the epileptic seizure occurs at the time of dental treatment steps taken to minimise the risk.

Cerebral Palsy

- Cerebral palsy, which occurs in two to three out of 1,000 live births, has multiple aetiologies resulting in brain injury that affects movement, posture, and balance.
- Cerebral palsy (CP) is a group of disorders that affect a person's ability to move and maintain balance and posture.
- Cerebral palsy is the most common motor disability in childhood.

Nelson used the term Cerebral palsy to describe a group of nonprogressive disorders resulting from malfunctioning of the motor centres and pathways of the brain.

Etiology

<p>Prenatal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brain malformations • In utero stroke • Congenital cytomegalovirus infection 	<p>Perinatal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hypoxic ischemic encephalopathy • Viral encephalitis • Meningitis
<p>Postnatal</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accidental head trauma • Anoxic insult • Child abuse 	<p>Prematurity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Premature deliveries • Low birth weight • Maternal infections

Classification of Cerebral Palsy¹

<p>According to Degree of Affected Areas</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mild • Moderate • Severe • No Cerebral Palsy 	<p>According to Topography</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Monoplegia • Diplegia • Hemiplegia • Paraplegia • Triplegia • Quadriplegia • Tetraplegia 	<p>According to Motor Function</p> <p>Spastic CP</p> <p>Nonspastic CP</p> <p>Ataxic CP</p> <p>Dyskinetic CP</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Athetoid • Dystonic <p>Mixed CP</p>	<p>Modified Swedish Classification</p> <p>Spastic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hemiplegia • Tetraplegia • Diplegia <p>Ataxic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Diplegia • Congenital (simple) <p>Dyskinetic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Choreoathetotic • Dystonic
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Clinical Manifestations

<p>(1) asymmetric tonic neck reflex, (2) tonic labyrinthine reflex, and (3) startle reflex</p> <p>Some of the common manifestations are:</p> <p>*Abnormalities of muscle tone</p> <p>*Delayed milestones</p> <p>*No control over movements</p> <p>*Muscle weakness</p> <p>*Spasticity and loss of coordination</p> <p>*Retention of primitive reflexes</p> <p>*Poor development of gross and fine motor control</p> <p>*Apraxia</p>	<p>Oral Manifestations</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • gastroesophageal reflux, as well as episodes of vomiting. • dental erosion, or loss of tooth structure. • Gingival overgrowth, due to seizure medications. • The head is tensely reclined • The mouth is open, and facial movements are tense. • The tongue is hypertonic and cigar-shaped (tongue thrust) • Misaligned and flared anterior
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Management¹⁴

<p>Behaviour Modification</p> <p>*Early morning appointments.</p> <p>*Make the child comfortable by Sensory Adapted Dental Environment (SADE) environment.</p> <p>*Voice control, tell-show-do (TSD) modelling.</p> <p>*Distraction technique - decrease the anxiety level like audio distraction, audio visual distraction etc.</p> <p>*Emphasize the importance of diet.</p>	<p>Modification In Radiographic Technique</p> <p>Extra-oral technique: Placement of reverse biting and 45° oblique head plate for patients having severe gag reflex.</p>
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Autism

Autism Spectrum Disorders (ASD) are a diverse group of conditions. They are characterized by some degree of difficulty with social interaction and communication. Other characteristics are atypical patterns of activities and behaviors, such as difficulty with transition from one activity to another, a focus on details, and unusual reactions to sensations.

History

The word Autism originated from a description by Jean Marc Gaspard Itard in 1801.

Bleuler in 1911 expressed autism "as loss of contact with the real world thereby experiencing difficulty in communication".

Leo Kanner (1943), an American child psychologist, described autism “as neurodevelopmental disorder presenting within the first three years of life”.

<p>Classification It consists of five subtypes, which include: (1) autism disorder (AD), (2) Asperger's syndrome, (3) Rett's disorder, (4) childhood disintegrative disorder (CDD), and (5) pervasive developmental disorder not otherwise specified (PDD-NOS)</p>	<p>Dental Findings of an Autistic Child¹ *Higher susceptibility to caries *Bruxism *Damaging oral habits *Traumatic injuries *Texture sensitivities *Gingivitis and poor oral hygiene</p>	<p>Management In Dental Office^{14,16} 1. Behavioural Management 2. Educational Management 3. Treatment Consideration • Dental clinic environment • Appointments • Modified treatment 4. Pharmacological Management</p>
<p>Behavior Management Communication Tell-Show-Do Restraints / Deep Pressure Touch Voice control Distractions Sensory techniques Social stories Aversive techniques</p>	<p>Treatment Consideration • Dental clinic environment • Appointment structure • Modified treatment</p>	<p>Educational Management • Family parental counselling • Previsit meeting • Carefully listening to the parents/caretakers is a key element in gaining their trust.</p>

Conclusion

Children with special health care needs often face neglected dental health, linked to their disabilities. Improved medical care has increased their prevalence, yet dental care remains overlooked. Pediatric dentistry now emphasizes comprehensive oral health care, aiming to normalize lives and extend lifespans through proper treatment.

References

- Gupta P V. Paediatric dentistry for special children. 1st edition 2016;3.
- T. M. Nelson, J. R. Webb (eds.), Dental Care for Children with Special Needs.
- Fiske J. Special Care Dentistry. 2007
- Marwah N. Textbook Of Paediatric Dentistry. 4th edition 2019.
- Centres for Disease Control and Prevention. Facts about developmental disabilities. Accessed 6 Jan 2018.
- American Academy of Pediatric Dentistry. Overview. *Pediatr Dent.* 2017;39(6):5–7
- Agerholm M. Handicaps and the handicapped: nomenclature and classification of intrinsic handicaps. *R Soc Health J.* 1975; 95:3-8.
- Scully C, Dios D P, Kumar N. *Special Care In Dentistry.* 1st Edition 2007.
- Tandon S. *Paediatric Dentistry.* 3rd Edition Vol.2
- Gupta P V. *Paediatric dentistry for special child.* 1st edition 2016;3.
- Tandon S. *Paediatric Dentistry.* 3rd Edition Vol.2
- Owens J, Dyer TA, Mistry K. People with learning disabilities and specialist services. *British Dental Journal.* 2010 Mar;208(5):203-5.
- Shah AH, Fateel A, Al-Nakhli O. Dentists and dental students' opinion regarding dental treatment of patients with special needs. *JPDA.* 2011 Apr;20(2):98-104.
- Marwah N. Textbook Of Paediatric Dentistry. 4th edition 2019.
- Chen X, Clark JJ. Assessment of dentally related functional competency for older adults with cognitive impairment - a survey for special-care dental professionals. *Special Care in Dentistry.* 2013 Mar;33(2):48-55.
- Rafique S, Fiske J, Palmer G, Daly B. Special care dentistry: part 1. Dental management of patients with inherited bleeding disorders. *Dental Update.* 2013 Oct 2;40(8):613-28.